

SEGMENTATION OF MEDICAL IMAGES USING A MIXTURE MODEL AND MORPHOLOGICAL FILTERING

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ABSTRACT

In this work a practical solution for segmenting 3D MR images is proposed. This method is based on a mixture model and Expectation Maximization (EM) algorithm. Here, we only focus on image segmentation which is used as a first step in our 3D compression and visualization system we are developing. A pretreatment based on gray-level thresholding followed by a morphological filtering is employed, then a stochastic segmentation method based on a finite mixture model is used. The obtained results confirm that statistical segmentation based on mixture model combined with Bayesian decision rule is a powerful tool for segmenting MR images.

KEYWORDS: 3D image, Compression, Estimation-Maximization, Mixture, Segmentation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since the first published papers on three dimensional visualization of medical images in the seventies a significant amount of effort has been spent in this direction [1]. A volume data is the sampled function of the three spatial dimensions. The typical example is the data generated from a set of CT or MR images. However, the size of the volume data is normally very large, so a compression method for volume data is needed [2], [3]. The compressed volume may be used for efficient previewing or initial study. In many applications, the original data should be retained for final evaluation. In computer graphics, hierarchical or multi-resolution techniques may be considered as form of data compression since they reduce the number or complexity of geometric primitives needed to describe a scene. However, most of previous works pay more attention to improving the rendering quality than analyzing the image content before rendering. Among the methods using some analysis pretreatments before visualizing the volume data, the approaches based on image segmentation have been proved to be powerful. Furthermore, it has been also proved that segmentation-based compression method is a powerful tool for storing such huge information with a

good quality [4]. In addition to that, region segmentation is often needed in some visualization of the volume data when only the rendering of a specific morphological structure is needed [3]-[6].

Generally, in segmentation-based visualization approaches, the first and crucial step is to identify object voxels by thresholding their attributes, such as in FT-B (Front-To-Back) method [2]. Since different tissues could have the same responses to the physical signal this may result in an unavoidable overlapping problem [2]. Among 3D image segmentation techniques, Expectation Maximization (EM) algorithm is proved to be an efficient solution [4], [7]. The use of EM-algorithm allows to estimate some statistical parameters corresponding to the voxel intensity distribution. These parameters permit to control the voxel classification using soft thresholding based on Bayesian decision rule.

The aim of this contribution is to describe our segmentation method used as a pretreatment in our segmentation-based compression and visualization system of 3D medical images we are developing. The paper is organized as follows: The EM method and its adaptation to Gaussian mixture are presented in section 2. The results and discussion are presented in section 3. Finally, a conclusion and perspectives are given in the last section.

2 THE METHOD

When applied on MR or CT images, the method described in the following operates in two steps. Firstly, a pretreatment based on automatic gray-level thresholding followed by a morphological filtering is employed. Applying only EM-based segmentation method without pretreatment, leads to an unsatisfactory result because of the uniform and noisy background of the image. This treatment allows to segment out the background which often introduces a bias in the statistical parameters estimation. In the second step, a stochastic segmentation method based on a finite mixture model is used. In the following, we firstly introduce the EM segmentation method and adapt it to mixture of Gaussian distributions.

2.1 EM-based Segmentation Method

When using the EM algorithm for segmenting 3D images, each voxel is considered as a mixture distribution realization of a random observation. The volume data could be then regarded as a set composed of different classes corresponding to the mixture laws. Here, a Gaussian mixture model is used since it is proved to be well suited for medical images [7]. The major interest of the Gaussian mixture is its capacity to produce a quick and useful approximation to a multi-modal histogram. The appeal of Gaussian distribution in the mixture is attributable to a large extent to the applicability of the EM algorithm [8] which maximizes a likelihood function. However, the use of the EM algorithm requires that the number of components in the mixture (the number of modes in the histogram) is available or could be determined using some known methods such that based on AIC criterion (Akaike's Information Criterion) [10]. Moreover, in order to avoid local minima, one has to choose carefully the initial values of the parameters [8], [9].

Since we deal with a mixture of Gaussians, the parameters to be estimated are respectively the means, the standard deviations and the mixing parameters of each component. The classical method for estimating these parameters is the Maximum Likelihood (ML) estimation. The technique for estimating proportions that assumes k classes of voxels in the image is now described. Each voxel x_j in the image is assumed to be distributed according to the following mixture law:

$$f(x_j) = \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i g_i(x_j | \mu_i, \sigma_i) \quad (1)$$

where, $i = 1, \dots, k$; α_i is the proportion of class i (the *a priori* probability of the class i), the $g_i(x_j | \mu_i, \sigma_i)$ are the conditional density probability functions given that the voxel is of class i , and $f(x_j)$ is the marginal probability density for each voxel. We assume that the conditional density functions are given by the Gaussian distribution.

$$g_i(x_j | \mu_i, \sigma_i) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi} \sigma_i} e^{-\frac{(x_j - \mu_i)^2}{2\sigma_i^2}} \quad (2)$$

where $\mu_i = E[x_j | X = i]$ is the mean and $\sigma_i^2 = E[(x_j - \mu_i)^2 | X = i]$ is the variance. The EM algorithm consists of the interactive application of the following essential two steps :

2.1.1 E-step

The E-step based on the current parameter estimates : the *a posteriori* probability that the cell i is responsible of the generation of pattern x_j is estimated as :

$$\beta_i(x_j) = \frac{\alpha_i^{old} g_i(x_j | \mu_i^{old}, \sigma_i^{old})}{\sum_{l=1}^k \alpha_l^{old} g_l(x_j | \mu_l^{old}, \sigma_l^{old})} \quad (3)$$

Where *old* stands for the previous estimated parameters.

2.1.2 M-step

This step, known as M-step, when applied to Gaussian mixture gives the following parameters estimates:

$$\alpha_i^{new} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \beta_i(x_j) \quad (4)$$

$$\mu_i^{new} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N x_j \beta_i(x_j)}{\sum_{j=1}^N \beta_i(x_j)} \quad (5)$$

$$(\sigma_i^{new})^2 = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N (x_j - \mu_i^{new})^2 \beta_i(x_j)}{\sum_{j=1}^N \beta_i(x_j)} \quad (6)$$

where N is the size of the image.

This iterative process stops when all the parameters do not sensibly change. The use of the EM algorithm to estimate the mixture parameters supposes that the number of components is available, which can be determined by another algorithm [8]. However, the number of components itself is not sufficient. Since the EM algorithm is an iterative algorithm, it requires accurate initial values of the parameters. This could be achieved using a multithresholding method such as ISODATA clustering algorithm [11] as described in the following. Once the parameters estimated, a crucial problem which very often occurs in medical images is the overlapping of the modes. Indeed, some tissues have nearly the same response in a given range. This increases the difficulty in segmenting such data. To cope with this problem, we use Bayesian rule, which means that each voxel belongs to the class C if, and only if,

$$C(x_j) = Arg \left[\max_{1 \leq i \leq k} \{ \alpha_i g_i(x_j | \mu_i, \sigma_i) \} \right] \quad (7)$$

where $i = 1, \dots, k$. Another solution for reducing the miss-classification error consists in exploiting the spatial correlation of voxels.

2.2 Parameters Initialization

Before applying the EM algorithm, we have chosen the iterative algorithm ISODATA [11] for initializing the parameters (the means and the variance), which works as following :

1. After an initial guess is made, at each iteration we get a new threshold in the following way.

Choose some initial values for the thresholds $T_1, T_2, \dots, T_C$, such that $T_0 \leq T_1 < T_2 < \dots \leq T_C$, where T_0, T_C are, respectively, the minimum and maximum gray-level, and C the number of classes.

2. Loop : Calculate the means using :

$$\mu_k = \frac{\sum_{i=T_{k-1}}^{i=T_k} i \times h(i)}{\sum_{i=T_{k-1}}^{i=T_k} h(i)} \quad (8)$$

Then update the thresholds $T_k^{new} = \frac{\mu_k + \mu_{k+1}}{2}$.

3. Update the means using (8).

4. If any mean has changed, go to Loop, otherwise, stop. The convergence of the algorithm is always guaranteed as demonstrated in [11].

Once the optimum parameters for initialization have been computed EM can start.

3 RESULTS ON SYNTHESIZED AND ACTUAL IMAGES

a. Original image.

b. Segmented image.

c. Gray-level histogram.

Figure 1: Stochastic segmentation of three Gaussian modes.

To test the efficiency of the proposed segmentation method, a synthesized image composed of three overlapping modes is used.

a. Original image.

b. Thresholded image.

c. Closing by a disc.

d. Reconstructed image.

e. Without background.

f. With background.

Figure 2: Stochastic segmentation steps of a MR image.

Fig. 1 shows the original noisy image, the segmented image, and the gray-level histogram (experimental and fitted), respectively. The original synthesized image is composed of three bands corrupted by a mixture of additive white gaussian noise (three different variances), segmenting such image without pretreatment is rather difficult task. Here it is proved that EM-based segmentation is less noise-sensitive as shown in Fig. 1b. To demonstrate the effectiveness of the parameters estimation the original histogram and the fitted one are displayed in 1c. We also applied the method to a MR image where four classes of voxels are assumed. But we have not obtained a satisfactory result because of the large fraction of the image occupied by the dark background which produces a sharp peak in the histogram leading to a bad estimation of the mixture parameters. To overcome this problem, a pretreatment using automatic gray-level thresholding [12] followed by morphological filtering, a gray-level closing, is used. Fig. 2 shows the results corresponding to the successive processing steps leading to the final segmented image Fig. 2e, where four classes of pixels are clearly identified. Fig. 2b shows the automatic thresholding of the original image, Fig. 2a, using Otsu's method, which has been proved to be one of the most efficient histogram-based thresholding methods [13]. Fig. 2c shows results after closing using a disc whose dimension depends upon the quality of the thresholded image. Fig. 2d shows the reconstructed image by geodesic dilating or erosion [14] to get the connected skull cluster as shown in Fig. 2d. The segmentation procedure is then applied only on this cluster of interest. Fig. 2f presents a comparison of the final result with background of the original image. Subjective evaluation clearly shows that the image of Fig. 2e is better segmented than that of Fig. 2f. Indeed, the regions frontiers are smooth and the noise reduced.

4 CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

The obtained results confirm that statistical segmentation based on mixture model combined with Bayesian decision rule is a powerful tool for segmenting MR images. This method has helped us to extract the desired regions and to estimate the distribution parameters of voxels in each region of the studied image. This segmentation method is used as a pretreatment for visualizing and compressing volume data. Another aspect under study is to exploit spatial correlation of voxels in the segmentation process.

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